

AROUND THE WORLD: PEDAGOGICAL METHODS FOR INCLUSIVE TRAINING OF PUPILS DURING THE FIRST STAGE OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The 'Around the World' curriculum in Bulgarian schools is designed to help young students aged 6-7 and 7-8 develop their personalities. The objectives are to improve their cognitive capacities, as well as to develop social skills and competencies. Learned knowledge of objective reality is critical to their effective adaptation, inclusion, socializing, and life preparation.*

Part of the experimental investigation with first and second grade students in the topic 'Around the globe' is explored in the publication. The goal is to detect the favorable impact of the pedagogical technology employed in the class to improve their cognitive capacities.

The pedagogical tools utilized in the social sphere have enhanced the learning content of inclusive education. Interactive-communicative learning approaches, artistic-illustrative and multimedia materials, and a set of tasks to consolidate and apply their knowledge are all provided. Control and experimental studies are carried out in two equal schools with first and second grade students.

Keywords: *pedagogical technologies, globalization, inclusive education, socialization, and students.*

1 INTRODUCTION

The 'Around the World' curriculum in Bulgarian schools is designed to broaden the social and cognitive horizons of young students (ages 6-7 and 7-8). '... is aimed at developing the foundations of the student personality - obtaining not only knowledge and information, but also comprehending the psychological traits and characteristics of the kid' [1]. Primary school students are constantly exposed to elements of their local natural and social environment, such as: native village locations and landmarks, people's labor and occupation, modes of transportation, nature and its conservation, relationships between family members, relationships between classmates and friends, human body and care, healthy lifestyle, national symbols, holidays, customs, and so on. The amount, quantity, and quality of knowledge are unique to each kid since they all have unique life experiences that are closely tied to their surroundings. They increased their understanding of the surrounding reality by studying the topics of the social realm of learning material. This information is also required for the acquisition of skills and competences that contribute to their effective adaptation, inclusion, and socialization - life preparation.

To begin, we would like to emphasize the following: in recent years, the Bulgarian educational system has undergone many changes aimed at overcoming discrimination, segregation, and marginalization of children from vulnerable groups, minority groups, disabled people, individuals with special educational needs, individuals with specific training difficulties, and others. It is reasonable for the aforementioned categories, however it seems that youngsters who do not have established difficulties need a supportive, exciting learning environment. Its establishment is one of the top aims of educational institutions. The new concept of a teacher, who

is an artist, a tutor, and even a friend, is supplemented by a motivator, a creative-innovative person who uses cutting-edge technology, and so on. It meets today's expectations by reacting to the particular requirements of each of the students with whom they work, which is fully consistent with the inclusive education philosophy: 'Art. 3. (1) Inclusive education is a process of recognizing, accepting, and supporting the uniqueness of each child or pupil, as well as the diversity of needs of all children and students, by activating and incorporating resources aimed at removing barriers to learning and creating opportunities for children and students to develop and participate in all aspects of community life. [6]. As a result of their efforts, teachers must continually update their teaching, methods, tools, and technologies - pedagogical, interactive, ICT, and so on - that contribute to the construction of a 'Supporting educational and informational environment. An environment in which information, digital, interactive, and ICT play an instrument, a tool in the hands of the contemporary Bulgarian teacher' [2].

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 The goal of an experimental investigation

This specific study's purpose is to discover the beneficial effect of the pedagogical technologies used in the lesson, aiming at strengthening the cognitive abilities and the creation of social skills and competencies of the children from the first stage of education on the topic 'Around the globe'. It is important to note that the authoring pedagogical technologies used serve to enrich the educational content with the aspect of inclusive education in social world topics, without requiring a change in the components or the chronology of the methodological-didactic structure of the lesson.

2.2 Research design

Figure 1 depicts the phases, algorithms, preset objectives, tasks, and so on that the dissertation research will go through. All of these components are linked and interlinked.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Scientific literature review and analysis in the realm of inclusive education Examine the egress level of cognitive activity of the students polled creation of a software platform based on the model The 'Around the World' learning topic (Primary and secondary school) Working with experimental classes is an application of the experimental model in practice. Creating a paradigm for 'Pedagogical Technologies for Inclusive Education' Examine the ingress level of cognitive activity of the students polled.

Figure 1 depicts the phases of the dissertation research.

Every beginning requires scientific literature investigation and analysis, in this instance in the subject of inclusive education. From September 2017 until September 2018, the time period is covered. Then we created a 'Pedagogical Technologies for Inclusive Education' model for students in the first and second grades of the 'Around the World' topic. We shall explore the dissertation research's underlying notions of 'Technology' and 'Pedagogical Technology' in a holistic manner.

The term 'technology' is derived from the Greek terms (tekhne) - art, mastery, skill, and (logos) - knowledge, science, and study.[5] According to D. Pavlov, 'any action aiming at reaching a specific outcome in the process of human formation and growth and which has a technical character may be labeled one or another sort of technology' [7]. Various writers have examined the concept of 'educational technology' in pedagogical literature.M. Koleva defines pedagogical technology as a "set of psychological-pedagogical facilities, defining the special set and components of forms, methods of education, educational resources; it is an organizational and

methodological tool for the realization of the pedagogical process," as well as "... systemic order and order of operation of all instrumental and personal means used to achieve pedagogical purposes" [4].

The model is an innovative pedagogical technology that aims to establish the positive impact of enhancing students' cognitive abilities and molding their social skills and competencies. The study of the ingress cognitive activity levels of the control and experimental groups was conducted in the first weeks of the school year at two comparable institutions. Using the devised exams, one for first grade and one for second, we evaluated the young students. The content of these questions reflects the topical distribution of the 'Around the World' subject with respect to 'Social World' topics. Students have individually completed tests printed on paper and filled out by hand. Implementing the experimental technological paradigm for inclusive education through labor in experimental courses was the next step. From September 2018 to December 2018, we implemented the model by teaching eight first-grade lessons and eight second-grade lessons. Developing a software platform for the 'Pedagogical Technologies for Inclusive Education' model; Examining the egress level of cognitive activity of the experimental and control group students; and Analyzing the results of the study are the subsequent steps.

2.3 Research technology. The teaching of the content of each subject is based on the Bloom Taxonomy levels, Figure 2.

The continual mastering and rising of each level enable students to study material according to their own talents and speed of learning, which is fully aligned with the inclusive education concept. The instruction is based on what is known as a combined lesson. It combines two types of educational organization: frontal and individual. It also integrates information sources: the instructor and advanced students [3]. The methodological-didactic structure of the lessons is as follows:

- Preliminary preparation: homework is used to update students' understanding of prior subjects. Asking topic-related questions or utilizing alternative tools such as crossword puzzles, wordplay, word discovery puzzles, riddles, musical puzzles, and so on are utilized in the conversational technique. A conversation-based approach is used to introduce them to the new subject, with a focus on questioning. This section of the course aids in the development of the first two levels of the Bloom Taxonomy, namely perception and comprehension. They are distinguished by actions such as description, enumeration, pointing, replication, explanation, and comparison.

- Main part: In this section of the class, the instructor develops cognitive abilities from the following two levels - application and analysis, which are components of the 'Pedagogical Technologies for Inclusive Education' model that has been adopted. It is a collection of instructional technologies aimed at enhancing and further displaying the content of the 'Around the World' theme, Figure 3.

The paradigm incorporates interactive-communicative techniques such as storytelling, interaction, and debate. The linguistic depiction of certain information determines its communication characteristics. The nature of interactive learning techniques in this context is a chance to actively engage students in the cognitive process via constant engagement and feedback to address challenging circumstances. Because of its monological nature and lesser student activity, the story technique is employed more sparingly. They often become passive listeners rather than active participants. Because focused inquiries establish a requirement for active

participation and application of gained information about the topic, phenomena, or process they are studying, the conversation technique is employed more often than other methods. Given that the topic 'Around the World' is intended to build a social and cognitive horizon among young students, another relevant strategy that is employed is debate. It is distinguished by learners sharing personal experience, opinions, and points of view while finding answers to a problem. Furthermore, kids develop tolerance in relationships and communication by listening to and embracing one other's opinions, as well as challenging and assessing them. We found the above methods to be effective because they help to stimulate and deepen pupils' mental activity, understand the information learned during the lesson, and form social and communicative skills and competences through continuous interaction with one another. The model's training tools include creative and illustrative resources, multimedia resources, and a complex of consolidation exercises and knowledge application. The creative and graphical materials we employ are mostly original picture material with content appropriate for the students' ages. It depicts the true appearance of things, events, and processes examined in class. This aids in additional illustration and promotes learning and comprehension.

'In recent years, the use of ICT, or information and communication technology, has progressively increased in popularity among educators and inside different educational institutions. Electronic and interactive tools and applications, e-learning software, and specialized hardware are already present in classrooms.' [8]. Modern youngsters choose the aforementioned technologies for pleasure and activities outside of the classroom, as well as for lesson and assignment preparation. The incorporation of multimedia materials in the model was necessitated by our goal to react to society's issues and needs for learners, as well as their demands for modernization of teaching techniques. In the experimental groups, the learning material is taught via PowerPoint presentations that incorporate images, tables, diagrams, and other graphics. At the same time, students are watching the presentations and actively engaging in classroom discussions. Where available and suitable, video assets used for supplemental visualization are included in certain subjects. The utilization of these resources seeks to enhance the learning material, which is believed to lead to an increase in learners' cognitive activity. The intricate set of tasks for information accumulation and application is a piece of instructional material designed for use by the general educator. The same tasks are assigned to all students in the studied class. Their purpose is to assess the degree of knowledge application on a specific topic.

CONCLUSION

In summation, we may conclude that in recent years, providing a supportive and inclusive learning environment has been one of the top concerns of institutions, professionals, instructors, and others working in the education area. Changes taken to address discrimination, segregation, and marginalization of children and vulnerable groups, minority groups, handicapped persons, individuals with special educational requirements, unique learning issues, and so on are now a reality and fully comply with the inclusive education concept.

The usage of various ICT in Uzbek schools has long been a truth. We concentrated on multimedia content, particularly PowerPoint presentations, when building the approach. The creative and pictorial materials supplied assist to better illustrate and enhance the curriculum content in the social world issues examined, as well as the objects, processes, and occurrences that are not always readily accessible for observation. The complexity of tasks could assist the teacher in identifying the need to provide general support for pupils' personality development, and the

presented model will assist current and future teachers in developing learning content as well as responding to the individual needs of each child and pupil, contributing to their successful socialization.

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